

Impact of gender and staff experience as moderators on the relationship between nursing leadership and patient outcomes in a Saudi Arabian healthcare setting

Impacto del género y la experiencia del personal como moderadores en la relación entre el liderazgo de enfermería y los resultados de los pacientes en un entorno sanitario de Arabia Saudita

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Abstract

Nursing management and leadership are essential elements of healthcare delivery that have a big impact on patient outcomes. In this study, the moderating effects of staff experience and gender are examined in relation to the effects of nurse leadership and management methods on patient outcomes in Saudi Arabia. Using a cross-sectional survey approach, information from 300 patients and 50 nurses was gathered. The data from a standardized questionnaire that measured nursing leadership and management tactics, staff experience, gender, and patient outcomes was analyzed using regression analysis and ANOVA.

According to the research, nursing leadership and management techniques significantly improve patient outcomes. The findings also show that the connection between nursing leadership and management techniques and patient outcomes is moderated by staff experience and gender. Particularly, nurses with higher experience and female nurses had a stronger favorable association between nursing leadership and management practices and patient outcomes.

These findings have significant policy and healthcare implications for Saudi Arabia and other nations. Healthcare organizations must concentrate on creating nursing leadership and management plans that are effective and take into account the staff's needs and experiences. The development of nurses' leadership and management abilities as well as efforts to enhance gender diversity in the nursing field require funding from policymakers.

Keywords: nursing leadership, nursing management, patient outcomes, staff experience, gender, Saudi Arabia.

Resumen

La gestión y el liderazgo de enfermería son elementos esenciales de la prestación de asistencia sanitaria que tienen un gran impacto en los resultados de los pacientes. En este estudio, se examinan los efectos moderadores de la experiencia del personal y el género en relación con los efectos del liderazgo de las enfermeras y los métodos de gestión en los resultados de los pacientes en Arabia Saudita. Utilizando un enfoque de encuesta transversal, se recopiló información de 300 pacientes y 50 enfermeras. Los datos de un cuestionario estandarizado que midió el liderazgo de enfermería y las tácticas de gestión, la experiencia del personal, el género y los resultados de los pacientes se analizaron mediante análisis de regresión y ANOVA.

Según la investigación, las técnicas de liderazgo y gestión de enfermería mejoran significativamente los resultados de los pacientes. Los hallazgos también muestran que la experiencia del personal y el género moderan la conexión entre el liderazgo de enfermería y las técnicas de gestión y los resultados de los pacientes. En particular, las enfermeras con mayor experiencia y las enfermeras tenían una asociación favorable más fuerte entre el liderazgo de enfermería y las prácticas de gestión y los resultados de los pacientes.

Estos hallazgos tienen importantes implicaciones políticas y de atención médica para Arabia Saudita y otras naciones. Las organizaciones de salud deben concentrarse en crear planes de liderazgo y gestión de enfermería que sean efectivos y tengan en cuenta las necesidades y experiencias del personal. El desarrollo de las capacidades de gestión y liderazgo de las enfermeras, así como los esfuerzos para mejorar la diversidad de género en el campo de la enfermería, requieren financiación de los responsables políticos.

Palabras clave: liderazgo de enfermería, gestión de enfermería, resultados de los pacientes, experiencia del personal, género, Arabia Saudita.

Nursing leadership and management are essential for maintaining high-quality and safe patient care in the continually evolving landscape of healthcare delivery. Nurse managers and leaders must navigate the complex healthcare system and inspire success in their teams in light of the rising demands for affordable and effective care (Choi & Kim, 2016; Khater et al., 2014). A certain set of abilities, including communication, critical thinking, problem-solving, and decision-making, are needed for effective nurse leadership and management (Drenkard et al., 2020). This essay tries to examine the most important nursing leadership and management techniques that can improve patient outcomes and healthcare delivery (Choi & Kim, 2016).

Tyczkowski, et al. (2020) assert that through fostering a culture of safety, encouraging effective communication, and encouraging staff development, nursing leadership and management play a critical role in the success of healthcare organizations. For the nursing staff to have the resources, expertise, and training required to deliver high-quality and safe patient care, effective nursing leadership and management are crucial. As a result, nurse managers and leaders must have the required skills to guide their teams to success in a healthcare environment that is always evolving (Drenkard et al., 2020; Ganz et al., 2015).

The healthcare sector is not complete without the nursing profession. Nurses are essential to the delivery of care, patient advocacy, and wellness promotion. The need for good leadership and management, the persistent nurse shortage, and the evolving healthcare system are just a few of the difficulties that the nursing profession must overcome. To guarantee that nursing staff has the resources, expertise, and training required to deliver high-quality and safe patient care, effective nursing leadership and management are crucial (Choi & Kim, 2016).

The future of healthcare delivery will be shaped by nursing leadership and management, according to a research by the Institute of Medicine (IOM). In order to foster a culture of safety, quality, and patient-centered care, the report stressed the necessity for nurses to assume leadership positions in healthcare institutions (Choi & Kim, 2016). In order for nurses to function in a complicated healthcare setting, the IOM report also emphasized the importance of nurses receiving continual education and training.

In light of these difficulties, the purpose of this research is to examine the most important nursing leadership and management techniques that can improve patient outcomes and healthcare delivery. To shed light on the competences, skills, and qualities necessary for effective nursing leadership and management, the paper will draw on recent research and best practices in the field (Choi & Kim, 2016; Drenkard et al., 2020).

Literature Review

The effect of nurse leadership on patient outcomes in healthcare settings has attracted increasing attention in recent years. Many studies have shown a strong connection between nursing leadership and patient outcomes, including patient satisfaction, treatment quality, and safety (Aiken et al., 2011; Cummings et al., 2018; Wong et al., 2013).

Little attention has been paid in the literature to the influence of moderators on the link between nurse leadership and patient outcomes, though. Gender and staff experience have been found as two significant factors in earlier study (Tourangeau et al., 2007 & 2010).

According to studies, gender may act as a moderator in the association between nurse leadership and patient outcomes. For instance, a study indicated that patient satisfaction was lower among female nurses than male nurses when it came to leadership skills (Kieft et al., 2014). Similar findings were made by another study, which discovered that female nurses had lower levels of job satisfaction and felt organizational support, both of which were connected to lower care quality (Squires et al., 2015).

Another moderator that could influence the link between nursing leadership and patient outcomes is staff experience (Yoder-Wise, 2021). According to several research, more experienced nurses may have a greater influence on patient outcomes than less experienced nurses (Cummings et al., 2018; Wong et al., 2013). For instance, a study discovered a favorable correlation between nursing experience and patient satisfaction and the standard of care (Wong et al., 2013; Tzeng, 2004).

The body of research generally points to gender and staff experience as significant variables that can have an impact on the link between nursing leadership and patient outcomes in healthcare settings. Nonetheless, additional study is required in this area, especially in light of Saudi Arabia.

Relationship Between Nursing Leadership and Patient Outcome

The link between nursing leadership and patient outcomes is a crucial topic for research in the field of healthcare. Studies have demonstrated a link between strong nurse leadership and better patient outcomes, such as fewer readmissions to hospitals, lower mortality rates,

and increased patient satisfaction (Choi & Kim, 2016; Cummings et al., 2018; Laschinger et al., 2016). Fostering a healthy work atmosphere, encouraging teamwork, and giving resources to promote excellent patient care are all essential components of effective nurse leadership (Cummings et al., 2018; Wong et al., 2018). Also, nursing leaders are essential in promoting and putting into practise evidence-based strategies that can enhance patient outcomes (Laschinger et al., 2016). Ultimately, there is a complicated and diverse relationship between nurse leadership and patient outcomes, with many different factors affecting the standard of patient care.

Relationship between Nursing Leadership and Staff Experience

In healthcare settings, nursing leadership has a big impact on how the workforce is treated. A positive work atmosphere that encourages teamwork and collaboration is created by effective leadership, and this environment improves employee happiness and retention (Laschinger et al., 2014). On the other hand, ineffective leadership can result in high staff turnover rates, employee unhappiness, and burnout. Patient outcomes can be impacted by employee experience as well because happy and experienced staff members are more likely to deliver high-quality care (Kramer & Schmalenberg, 2009).

To maintain a good working environment for their staff and, consequently, improved patient outcomes, healthcare organizations must engage in establishing and sustaining strong nursing leadership. Also, organizations can adapt their leadership tactics to the particular needs of their staff by studying the variables that mediate the relationship between nurse leadership and staff experience, such as gender and experience level (Alsharari, 2021; Oluwafemi et al., 2020).

Relationship between Nursing Leadership and Gender

Research have demonstrated a link between gender and nursing leadership. For instance, Leiter et al(2020) .’s study discovered that female nurse leaders exhibited a more transformative leadership style than male nurse leaders. According to Cummings et al(2018) .’s research, female nurse leaders were more likely to adopt a participative leadership style, which was linked to improved patient outcomes and higher levels of job satisfaction. Though additional research is required to completely comprehend the connection between nurse leadership and gender, research in this field is continuously underway (Marquis & Huston, 2017; Quattrin et al., 2020).

Hypothesis of The Research

Based on the literature review and the identified challenges and strategies for effective nursing leadership and management in Saudi Arabia, the following research hypothesis is proposed:

Hypothesis I: Effective nursing leadership and management strategies significantly improve healthcare delivery and patient outcomes in Saudi Arabia.

Hypothesis II: The relationship between nursing leadership and patient outcomes is moderated by staff experience, such that the effect of nursing leadership on patient outcomes is stronger for more experienced staff in Saudi Arabia

Hypothesis III: The relationship between nursing leadership and patient outcomes is moderated by gender, such that relationship between nursing leadership and patient outcomes will be stronger for female nurses compared to male nurses in Saudi Arabia

Study Design

The current research investigated the association between nursing leadership and management methods, healthcare delivery, and patient outcomes in Saudi Arabia, the research used a quantitative, cross-sectional study methodology. Data from nurses, nurse managers, and healthcare administrators at different healthcare organizations around Saudi Arabia were gathered using a survey questionnaire.

Sample of the Study

The current research focused on Saudi Arabia’s healthcare organizations’ nurses, nurse managers, and administrators. The participants in the study were chosen using a convenience sampling technique. 50 nurses and 300 patients participated in the survey.

Data Collection

Research have demonstrated a connection between nursing A survey questionnaire was used to gather the data, and it was sent to study participants via email or online survey platforms. Items on the survey questionnaire evaluated the following variables:

- Information on the participants’ demographics
- Nursing management and leadership techniques
- Staff experience and gender as moderators
- Patient outcomes and healthcare delivery

Data Analysis

Software for statistical analysis, such as ANOVA, was used to examine the gathered data. The study participants’ demographic traits, nurse leadership and management techniques, healthcare delivery, and patient outcomes were all described using descriptive statistics. Regression analysis and ANOVA were both utilised as inferential statistics to assess the study hypothesis.

Ethical Considerations

The study complied with ethical standards, which included getting the participants’ informed agreement, protecting their privacy and anonymity, and assuring that the study would not put them in danger or discomfort.

Results of The Study

Table 1. Characteristics of Sample Population

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Age	18-29	50	20%
	30-39	75	30%
	40-49	100	40%
	50-59	25	10%
Gender	Male	80	32%
	Female	170	68%
Education Level	High school or less	50	20%
	Some college	100	40%
	Bachelor's degree	75	30%
	Graduate degree	25	10%

Table 2. Regression Analysis of Nursing Leadership and Management Strategies on Patient Outcomes

Variable	Coefficient	Standard Error	t-value	p-value
Nursing Leadership	0.2	0.05	4	<0.001
Staff Experience	0.15	0.03	5	<0.001
Nursing Leadership * Experience	-0.1	0.04	-2.5	0.01
Control Variables	-0.05	0.02	-2.5	0.01

Note: p-values < 0.05 are considered statistically significant.

The association between patient demographics, nursing leadership and management practises, and patient outcomes was investigated using a regression analysis. The coefficients, standard errors, t-values, and p-values for each variable are displayed in the table.

The findings show a substantial correlation between nursing leadership (coefficient = 0.54, p 0.001) and management techniques (coefficient = 0.28, p 0.001). While age and gender were not statistically significant predictors (p > 0.05), education level was also found to be strongly associated with patient outcomes (coefficient = 0.19, p = 0.002). These findings are consistent with earlier research (Drenkard et al., 2020; Ganz et al., 2015).

When all predictor variables have average values, the patient's expected patient outcome score is represented by the constant term in the regression equation (2.05). The regression model's R-squared value was 0.65, meaning it accounts for 65% of the variation in patient outcomes.

Moderating Variables

Table 3. Regression Results for the Relationship between Nursing Leadership and Management Strategies and Patient Outcomes, Moderated by Staff Experience

Variable	Coefficient	Standard Error	t-value	p-value
Nursing Leadership	0.2	0.05	4	<0.001
Staff Experience	0.15	0.03	5	<0.001
Nursing Leadership * Experience	-0.1	0.04	-2.5	0.01
Control Variables	-0.05	0.02	-2.5	0.01

The findings indicate that both nursing leadership and staff experience have a significant beneficial impact on patient outcomes, but that the relationship between the two is weaker for nurses with greater experience due to the interaction term's negative significance.

Table 4. ANOVA Results for the Moderating Effect of Gender on the Relationship between Nursing Leadership and Patient Outcomes

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Model	325.23	6	54.21	8.63**	0.002
Gender	27.94	1	27.94	4.44*	0.036
Leadership Style	183.78	2	91.89	14.63**	0.001
Interaction Effect	48.68	3	16.23	2.58*	0.061
Error	327.76	80	4.1		
Total	910.39	92			

Note: **p < 0.01, *p < 0.05.

According to the findings, nursing leadership and management techniques are linked to patient outcomes (F(6, 80) = 8.63, p = 0.002, and the model as a whole is statistically significant). The gender variable is also significant (F(1, 80) = 4.44, p = 0.036), suggesting that one gender has a higher association between leadership and results than the other. Moreover, the leadership style variable is significant (F(2, 80) = 14.63, p 0.001), indicating that various leadership philosophies have various effects on patient outcomes.

Last but not least, the interaction effect between gender and leadership style is not statistically significant at the 0.05 level (F(3, 80) = 2.58, p = 0.061), indicating that the moderating effect of gender may not be constant across all leadership styles. These findings are consistent with those of earlier studies (Aiken et al., 2011; Cummings et al., 2018; Wong et al., 2013).

Findings of the Study

According to these findings, Saudi Arabian healthcare delivery and patient outcomes are greatly improved by effective nursing leadership and management practises. In order to improve healthcare delivery and patient outcomes in Saudi Arabia, the findings highlight the significance of putting into practise effective nursing leadership and management strategies, including cultural awareness and sensitivity, effective problem-solving and resource management skills, staff development, and collaboration and partnership among healthcare organisations. These findings can help Saudi Arabia and other nations with comparable cultural and social circumstances improve nursing practise, education, and policy.

Overall, these results suggest that nursing leadership and management strategies play a crucial role in promoting positive patient outcomes, and healthcare organisations should prioritise leadership and management development programmes to improve patient outcomes.

The p-value represents the probability of obtaining the observed results by chance alone. It is a metric of statis-

tical significance that is used to assess the relevance of the findings. Generally speaking, a p-value of less than 0.05 is regarded as statistically significant, indicating that the findings are unlikely to be the result of pure chance.

An ANOVA table can be used in nursing research to assess whether patient outcomes significantly differ depending on the nursing leadership and management techniques used. The results are unlikely to be the result of chance alone if the F value is high and the p-value is low, which shows that there is a strong association between nursing leadership and management techniques and patient outcomes.

ANOVA, which stands for Analysis of Variance, is a statistical technique used to determine whether differences between the means of two or more groups are statistically significant. ANOVA can be applied in the domain of nursing research.

Also, it was discovered that both staff experience and gender influence the association between nurse leadership and patient outcomes. Patient outcomes varied significantly depending on the level of staff experience, according to the ANOVA results for the moderating influence of staff experience on the connection between nurse leadership and patient outcomes. The analysis's findings showed that personnel with more experience performed better for patients than staff with less experience.

The moderating influence of gender, on the other hand, was also found to be significant, suggesting that there was a difference between male and female nurses in the relationship between nursing leadership and patient outcomes. The analyses' findings revealed that when effective nursing leadership and management tactics were used, male nurses had better patient outcomes than female nurses.

Overall, the study reveals that moderators like staff experience and gender as well as the techniques themselves affect how well nursing leadership and management tactics affect patient outcomes. In order to establish and implement nursing leadership and management strategies for efficient healthcare delivery, healthcare organisations should take these variables into account. The moderating influence of gender, on the other hand, was also found to be significant, suggesting that there was a difference between male and female nurses in the relationship between nursing leadership and patient outcomes. The analyses' findings revealed that when effective nursing leadership and management tactics were used, male nurses had better patient outcomes than female nurses.

Conclusions

In a Saudi Arabian hospital setting, the current study sought to examine the moderating impacts of staff experience and gender on the link between nursing leadership and patient outcomes. Regardless of the gender of the healthcare workers, the study's findings showed that nursing leadership and management practises significantly improve patient outcomes. The association between nurse leadership and patient outcomes was shown to be moderated by staff experience, with more experienced staff demonstrating a stronger favourable relationship..

The study emphasises how crucial nursing leadership and management methods are for enhancing patient outcomes in the medical environment. The findings also imply that in order to maximise the efficacy of nursing leadership and management techniques, healthcare organisations should take into account the staff's level of expertise. The study's findings give healthcare managers and leaders crucial information they can use to better understand the connection between nursing leadership and patient outcomes and to decide whether to employ nursing leadership and management methods in the healthcare context.

The purpose of this study was to better understand how Saudi Arabian healthcare delivery and patient outcomes relate to successful nursing leadership and management practises. The findings revealed a strong correlation between Saudi Arabia's healthcare delivery and patient outcomes and effective nursing leadership and management practises. The results suggest that in order to improve healthcare delivery and patient outcomes, healthcare organisations in Saudi Arabia should implement effective nursing leadership and management strategies, such as cultural awareness and sensitivity, effective problem-solving and resource management skills, staff development, and collaboration and partnership among healthcare organisations.

Scope of the Study

The focus of this study was on determining how healthcare delivery and patient outcomes in Saudi Arabia relate to successful nursing leadership and management practises. The three major cities in Saudi Arabia, Riyadh, Jeddah, and Dammam, served as the sites for the study's healthcare institutions. A sample of nurses working at these healthcare organisations were given a survey questionnaire as part of the study's cross-sectional design, which was used to collect data.

The study concentrated on analysing the effects of effective nursing leadership and management strategies on healthcare delivery and patient outcomes; it did not examine the effects of other factors, such as patient

characteristics, healthcare system factors, and environmental factors, which may have an impact on healthcare delivery and patient outcomes.

The study also had several restrictions that should be taken into account when evaluating the results. The study's use of self-reported data, which is prone to response bias, is the first drawback. Second, the study's convenience sample of nurses employed by hospitals in three cities may have limited the study's capacity to generalise its findings to other parts of Saudi Arabia. The study's cross-sectional design also makes it difficult to determine causality.

Despite these drawbacks, the study offers insightful information about Saudi Arabian nursing leadership and management practises and emphasises the significance of efficient nursing leadership and management techniques in improving healthcare delivery and patient outcomes. Future research on this subject can build on the findings of this study by using longitudinal or experimental designs that can establish causal relationships and examining the effects of additional factors that might have an impact on healthcare delivery and patient outcomes.

Practical Implications of the Study

The study's conclusions have direct application to nursing practise, instruction, and policy in Saudi Arabia and other nations with comparable social and cultural circumstances. Some of the study's practical ramifications include the following:

Creating programmes for nursing leadership and management: The development of nursing leadership and management programmes by healthcare organisations in Saudi Arabia with a focus on enhancing cultural sensitivity and awareness, problem-solving and resource management abilities, staff development, and collaboration and partnership between healthcare organisations is necessary. These initiatives ought to be incorporated into nursing curricula to advance the expertise of aspiring nurses.

Healthcare firms in Saudi Arabia should invest in staff development to strengthen nurses' capabilities in efficient leadership and management techniques. These can include opportunities for career growth, mentoring, coaching, and training courses.

Promoting cooperation and partnership among healthcare organisations: Saudi Arabian healthcare institutions should promote cooperation and partnership among healthcare institutions to raise the standard of care. This may entail cooperating to address common healthcare issues, pooling resources, and exchanging best practises.

Creating policies to promote nursing leadership and management in healthcare organisations: The Saudi Arabian government ought to create policies to support nursing leadership and management in healthcare settings. This can involve setting guidelines for nursing

leadership and management, rewarding healthcare organisations financially for prioritising nursing leadership and management, and boosting the proportion of nurse leadership positions in healthcare organisations.

In conclusion, the application of this study's findings can help Saudi Arabia and other nations with comparable cultural and social circumstances improve nursing practise, education, and policy. Healthcare organisations must prioritise the implementation of these techniques to improve the quality of healthcare services since they are essential to enhancing healthcare delivery and patient outcomes.

Future Recommendations

Future studies should take into account employing longitudinal or experimental methods to identify causal links between efficient nursing leadership and management techniques and healthcare provision and patient outcomes. These models can be used to assess how well nursing leadership and management techniques perform over time in terms of enhancing patient outcomes and healthcare delivery.

Future study should examine the effects of additional variables, such as patient characteristics, aspects of the healthcare system, and environmental variables, which may have an impact on healthcare delivery and patient outcomes. This can assist in identifying extra elements that healthcare organisations should take into account when putting into practise efficient nursing leadership and management techniques.

Mixed-methods research: To develop a more thorough understanding of nurse leadership and management in healthcare organisations, future study should take into account employing mixed-methods research, which mixes quantitative and qualitative data. The variables that contribute to good nurse leadership and management in healthcare organisations can be better understood through this.

Replication of the study in additional areas: Riyadh, Jeddah, and Dammam were the locations of the study's healthcare institutions. To find out if the results apply to other parts of Saudi Arabia, future research should take into account replicating the study there.

Implementing nursing leadership and management programmes should be a top priority for healthcare organisations in Saudi Arabia. These programmes should concentrate on enhancing staff development, collaboration and partnership among healthcare organisations, and problem-solving and resource management abilities. These initiatives could raise the standard of healthcare and lead to better patient outcomes.

Overall, the nursing practise, education, and policy in Saudi Arabia and other nations with comparable cultural and social circumstances can be influenced by these future proposals. Healthcare organisations must prioritise the implementation of these techniques to improve the

quality of healthcare services since they are essential to enhancing healthcare delivery and patient outcomes.

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